

ACHIEVING ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE IN BLACK COMMUNITIES: A COMPARISON BETWEEN KENYA AND USA.

With the ever-increasing socioeconomic inequalities, and environmental, some have started to argue that there is a correlation between environmental rights, environmental law and jurisprudence, and how the various governments have become increasingly involved in resolving dilemmas affecting environmental justice. Issues of aligning governments to meet the challenges of sustainable development have been ranked among the top emerging quagmires of the 21st century. However, the concept of environmental justice arose as another key theme in the 21st century; that involves policy issues not recognized, in general, environmental ideologies, which concern strict ecology matters. Using case studies, the paper argues that current environmental injustices have roots in colonial laws and systemic racism perpetrated over the past years.

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INTRODUCTION

With the ever-increasing socioeconomic and environmental inequalities, some have started to argue that there is a correlation between environmental rights, environmental law, and jurisprudence, and how the various governments have become increasingly involved in resolving dilemmas affecting environmental justice (United Nations Environmental Programme, 2012). Subsequently, the younger generation will predominantly rely upon their government and communities to provide a resolution to these types of injustice and are seeking the implementation of a detailed framework of principles and laws that can help with better measures to support marginalized communities.

Additionally, issues of aligning governments to meet sustainable development challenges have been ranked among the top emerging quagmires of the 21st century. Sustainable development was defined by the Brundtland Commission as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Keeble, 1988). However, the concept of environmental justice arose as another key theme in the 21st century; that involves policy issues not recognized, in general, environmental ideologies, which concerns strict ecology matters.

The 1992 Rio Declaration succinctly captures the key components of environmental justice. It explains that environmental issues are best handled with the participation of all concerned citizens. It is fundamental to note that nationally, everyone should have appropriate access to information regarding the environment held by public authorities, including knowledge of hazardous materials and activities in their communities, and the opportunity to participate in decision-making processes. Further, it impels the States to facilitate and encourage public awareness and participation by making data widely available. In addition, states are to provide effective access to judicial and administrative proceedings, involving redress and remedy (United Nations General Assembly, 1992).

This paper will discuss the concept of environmental justice as a tool for effective management of natural resources in the Kenyan and USA context. Further, it will be examining how environmental justice is inextricably related to sustainable development. Hence, we will be exploring the role multilateral institutions such as the United Nations Permanent Forum of People of African Descent has in assessing whether the laws, policies and regulations under study distribute environmental burdens proportionately; whether they have adequate provisions for all to participate in environmental decision-making and whether I/they allow all to have access and enjoy a fair share of natural resources. However, access to, control and use of natural resources in both parts of the USA and Kenya has been limited, denied, or undermined by laws and policies. Using case studies, the paper argues that current environmental injustices have roots in colonial laws and systemic racism perpetrated over the past years.

***SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IS
“DEVELOPMENT THAT MEETS THE
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FUTURE GENERATIONS TO MEET
THEIR OWN NEEDS”***

In Kenya, current environmental injustices have their roots in colonial laws and policies which imposed inequitable environmental burdens and marginalized certain communities from enjoying access to and a fair share of the country’s natural resources such as territories, water, and a clean and safe environment. Therefore, environmental justice in Kenya centres mainly on formulating and implementing environmental regulations, decisions, and public policy that promote equitably.

In the USA, the environmental justice concept had its genesis in the late 1970s and early 1980s (McGurty, 1997). As a reaction to the prejudiced and biased distribution of unwanted land usually regarded as Locally Undesirable Land

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Uses (LuLus) (Bullard, 1996) – such as the sites for hazardous waste, landfills, incinerators, and zoning of polluting industries – that were skewed towards neighbourhoods where visible minorities lived. This extended many to the exclusion of, or limited participation by people of colour and other minorities when environmental policy and laws were made (Aswan, 1997). The concept of environmental racism - the disproportionate allocation of environmental risks to coloured communities- further includes discriminatory practices or policies that limit or omit marginalized groups from enjoying the right to a healthy environment. These practices are seen in uneven negative impacts of environmental laws, asymmetrical access to environmental services such as waste removal, or inadequate maintenance of environmental amenities such as parks and recreation areas.

TERMINOLOGY

Environmental Justice and Racism

Environmental justice is a movement that started in 1978 after multiple protests occurred because of a highly dangerous chemical spilled on a mainly black and brown town. The ideology refers to “the fair treatment and meaningful involvement of all people regardless of race, colour, national origin, or income concerning the development, implementation and enforcement of environmental laws and policies” (Environmental Justice, 2021).

On the other hand, **environmental racism** is connected to the concept of systemic racism. In 1982, civil rights activist Benjamin Chavis defined “environmental racism” as the

“racial discrimination in environmental policy-making, the enforcement of regulations and laws, the deliberate targeting of people of colour for toxic waste facilities, the official sanctioning of the life-threatening presence of poisons and pollutants in our communities, and the history of excluding people of colour from the leadership of the ecology movements” (Beech, 2020). Hence, it refers to policies, laws and practices that were put in place to negatively impact marginalized communities. Regulations such as racially segregated housing, the ban on black donors and the three-strikes law are examples of systemic discriminatory policies.

A Green Economy

A **green economy** is defined by the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP, 2012) as “low carbon, resource-efficient and socially inclusive”. In a Green Economy, growth in employment and income is driven by public and private investment into such economic activities, infrastructure and assets that allow reduced carbon emissions and pollution, enhanced energy and resource efficiency and prevention of the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services (UNEP). Consequently, growth in employment and remuneration is controlled by the public and private interests. There are two essential purposes of environmental justice. The first is that one group does not bear an extra burden from the repercussions of climate change. Second, it gives an equal opportunity for everyone to be able to participate and make decisions that would be best for their region and country.

Migration and Food Security

As a basic human right, **food security** is an emerging issue but has been qualified as one of the top issues worldwide. In 1996, the World Food Summit defined food security as “exists when all people, at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life” (Fiat Panis, 2006). Famine and hunger often go together and about 800

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million people experience a lack of food. This is especially troubling to know as most of the individuals dying of this injustice are children. In 2020 and 2021 the United Nations acknowledge that Yemen has suffered from one of the worst famines in the 21st century. The idea of food security does not only impact developing countries, even developing nations are predisposed by it. In the United States, 1 out of 8 Americans goes hungry, that is about 38 million Americans, with a very disturbing number of 12 million children. This is the result of socio-economic problems such as poverty, and not having access to healthcare.

There is a direct correlation between **migration** and food security. In certain areas where instability is due to wars, poverty and diseases, there is human and animal migration, “a movement of a group of people from one place to another. There is much uncertainty around their life as they move as nomads” (United Nations, 2000). In the case of the United States, after the devastation of Hurricane Katrina, most displaced individuals were part of the African American community. The lack of government investment and help contributed to the region’s slow recovery (Neuman, 2015). In rural areas of Kenya, migration is especially hard when there are children. In fact, according to statistics, the likelihood of migration is increased when the woman who has attended school is in her twenties and not married (Migration Policy Institute, 2003).

Low-Income Housing Proximity to Landfill and Highly Polluted Areas

Low-income housing is defined by Canada Mortgage and Housing Corporation as “housing which is deemed affordable to those with a household income at or below the median as rated by the national government or a local government by a recognized housing affordability index. Most of the literature on affordable housing refers to mortgages and several forms that exist along a continuum – from emergency homeless shelters to transitional housing, to non-market rental (also known as social or subsidized housing), to the formal and informal rental, indigenous housing, and ending with affordable home ownership” (Canada Mortgage and Housing Corporation, 2018).

While these homes may seem affordable, they can also result in housing segregation. Since the 1970s, the idea of segregated housing has BEEN related to two major aspects: race and poverty. Racially segregated housing is one of the principal causes of racial inequalities. It is defined as “the physical separation of the races by enforced residence in certain areas. IT is an institutional mechanism of racism that was designed to protect whites from social interaction with blacks” (William & Collins, 2001). Racially segregated housing was mainly prominent in predominantly white countries such as Canada, England, and the United States, but also in Black countries such as South Africa and Kenya. However, with the rise of the Civil Rights Movement and decolonization, many western nations and former colonies have reneged on the notion of racially segregated housing and have adopted economic segregation housing.

Economically segregated housing means that “wealth is concentrated into very select pockets of the city. It keeps neighbourhoods divided: politically, academically, and culturally. The result is a city where some places are zones of incredible opportunity while other places dramatically limit people’s ability to thrive” (Munson, 2017). Hence, depending on individual wealth, higher-income individuals are more likely to afford homes in safer neighbourhoods and benefit from better municipal, and governmental services. The problem is that many marginalized communities whose descendants were affected by racially segregated housing are not able to afford homes in richer neighbourhoods because of systemic racism and inequality. Subsequently, low-income housing will be predominately placed in highly polluted areas such as Flint, Michigan.

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Environmental Colonialism

The concept of **environmental colonialism** is referred to as “the various ways in which colonial practices have impacted the natural environments of Indigenous Peoples” (Duquette, 2020). Therefore, environmental colonialism addresses the exploitation of resources in former colonies such as most nations in the African continent and Latin and Caribbean countries. Thus, the exploitations of those countries allowed the disaster to alteration of their ecosystem (Duquette, 2020).

In Kenya for example, there are lots of ancestral grounds and lands that were wrongfully used by the imperial countries which resulted in environmental destruction. As a result, even if Kenya is one of the most advanced nations when it comes to the fight against climate change, the country suffers from major famines and environmental catastrophes (Bhalla, 2021). On the other hand, the United States, which is one of the most economically developed suffers like Kenya. Rather, its environmental colonialism comes from the extreme exploitation of resources that affects mainly marginalized communities.

CLIMATE CHANGE AND AFRICAN DESCENT

On December 11, 1997, countries such as Canada and Kenya signed the Kyoto Protocol, which is considered the first major international treaty in which the signatory nations committed to reducing their greenhouse gas emission. Therefore, “[...] the Kyoto Protocol operationalizes the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change by committing industrialized countries and economies in transition to limit and reduce greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions by agreed individual targets” (United Nations Climate Change, -).

The protocol came into effect in 2008, however, it had little impact since major developed countries, such as the United States decided not to sign. The United States argued that global warming was a product of developing nations such as India and China; subsequently, these developing countries should reduce their emissions. One significant challenge of the Kyoto Protocol is that heavily industrialized countries like the United States, considered one of the biggest emitters, did not ratify the protocol citing economic reasons. Despite contributing relatively little to global emissions, a lot of burdens have been unfairly placed on less-developed countries in Africa and other parts of the world to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Malakoff, 2007). Furthermore, in 2011, under Prime Minister Stephen Harper, the then Environment Minister Peter Kent claimed that Canada should opt out of the agreement because major players such as China and the United States were not members of the protocol. Hence, under the Harper government, Canada pulled out of the protocol (Curry & McCarthy, 2011).

Historically, Kenya was denied many resources through policies and laws that were created and passed during the colonial period. Additionally, statements made by powerful countries such as the United States during the signature of the Kyoto Protocol can be argued as blaming former colonies for all environmental issues without taking into consideration the contribution of environmental colonialism. In the post-colonial era, there have been conversations about all the natural resources and their exportation. However, even with its colonial history and the consequences of environmental racism, Kenya is considered one of the leading African countries in the fight against climate change (USAID, 2018). Even though Kenya is a key player against climate change, the country’s main economy depends on rain-fed agriculture and tourism. As a result of environmental consequences such as the increase in recurrent heat waves and droughts, the country has seen an increase in displacement, loss of livestock and famine (USAID, 2018).

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On the other hand, the United States' early refusal to sign the Kyoto Protocol and to recognize its massive contribution to the production of greenhouse gas emissions has had a major impact on the international fight against climate change. Furthermore, domestically the United States has demonstrated many times its lack of climate action, within its borders, especially when the issue affects mainly marginalized communities (Williamson, 2021). For example, in the Flint crisis, an ongoing crisis since 2014, the city is a predominantly black community. Many have accused the government of neglecting this community based on race and economic status (Williamson, 2021).

THE DURBAN AGREEMENT FOR ENHANCED ACTION

In 2011, the National Delegations met at the 17th session of the Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change in Durban, South Africa to launch a new round of discourses aimed at "developing a protocol, another legal instrument or an agreed outcome with legal force" (UNFCCC, 2012) to approach the current global climate crisis. This international climate deliberation also referred to as The Durban Platform for Enhanced Action sought to reinforce existing climate systems by extending the Kyoto Protocol for a second commitment period and beginning an advanced process to negotiate a post-2020 climate regime (Rajamani, 2012).

The Durban Agreement was a necessary response to address the emission-reduction commitment gaps that might arise at the expiration of the first commitment period of the Kyoto Protocol in 2012. It has been hailed because it provides the opportunity for a second commitment period of the Kyoto Protocol, the launch of the Green Climate Fund (HFW, 2012) and changed the developed-developing countries' disparity because more developing nations committed to the emission targets, compared to the initial Kyoto agreements where only so-called developed countries accepted emission reduction targets (Charlotte et al., 2012). With its attributable success, the DPEA has significant challenges, and it is instructive to assess summarily the implications of these challenges for developing, African countries and nations populated by people of African Descent.

The establishment of the Green Climate Fund aims to mobilize funding for low-emission and climate-resilient projects targeting particularly societies most exposed to the climate crisis - Least Developed Countries, Small Island Developing States, and African States. However, bureaucracy and poor funding commitment by developed countries are some of the identified challenges bedeviling the effectiveness of the Fund. As the next Convention on Climate Change in Egypt approaches, parties should guarantee that the welfare of countries vulnerable to climate change impacts receives renewed attention through equitable climate financing and implementation of actionable commitments in the Durban agreement to reduce emissions ensuring no one is left behind as the world addresses our collective climate emergency.

THE DECADE FOR PEOPLE OF AFRICAN DESCENT

On December 23, 2013, the United Nations General Assembly adopted the Decade for People of African Descent. The resolution recognized people of African Descent as distinct communities and that their human rights should be enabled and protected. According to Michelle Bachelet, the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights stated that "The Decade is a unique platform that emphasizes the important contribution made by people of African descent to every society and promotes concrete measures to stop discrimination and promote their full inclusion" (UN High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2014).

The United Nations has established three comprehensive action programmes to cover the proclamation. First, nations should advance the diverse heritages of people of African descent and their accomplishments in the development of various societies. With its history of slavery, inequality, and exploitation, many of the historical and cultural achievements of people of African Descent have been misplaced, erased, or changed to fit into the imperial agenda, later adopted by western countries (UN High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2014). Consequently, by

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recognizing the contribution of people in African, the resolution is attempting to remove the global unequal historical representations.

Second, the Decade for People of African Descent is trying to strengthen international, national, and regional programmes that do not discriminate and can be enjoyed by all. It aims to discourage countries from endorsing racially insensitive or racist Programmes against people of African descent (UN High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2014). Historically, there have been many countries, in the past, promoting, and adopting racist programmes that have stopped people of African from progressing.

The last point of the proclamation is to fortify international, national, and regional policies and judicial systems following the Programme of Action and the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination and the Durban Declaration. Hence, to ensure that all legal framework adopted by the government does not promote any discrimination or racist behaviour towards marginalized communities (UN High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2014).

On August 2, 2021, the United Nations General Assembly formally operationalized the Permanent Forum of People of African Descent as a platform for improving the quality of life and safety of people of African descent (UN High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2014). The Forum will serve as an advisory body to the United Nations Human Rights Council and support environmental justice while combating environmental racism.

THE PARIS AGREEMENT

The Paris Agreement signed by world leaders on 12 December 2015 during the United Nations Climate Change Conference, was meant to tackle the growing climate change concern and limit its negative by-products (The Paris Agreement). The legally binding treaty endorsed by 193 parties sets long-term goals to guide nations to better their response to the climate crisis. These intents include working towards a consequential reduction of global greenhouse emissions to attenuate the increase in global temperature, evaluating signatories' resolution to those targets every five years and offering significant financial support to so-called developing countries to ensure that they have the means to put in position the transformations to reach those goals (The Paris Agreement). The Paris Agreement comes with an obligation for all members to apply in place a Nationally Determined Contribution in the form of a five-year national climate action plan, in which states describe concrete commitments they will take to decrease greenhouse gas emissions and present how they arrange to build resilience to adapt to the climate crisis (The Paris Agreement). Signatories are strongly encouraged to present long-term strategies agreements although they are not mandatory.

THE THREE STATES OF INTEREST IN THIS PAPER NAMELY CANADA, KENYA AND THE UNITED STATES ALL SIGNED THE PARIS AGREEMENT IN 2015.

The three states of interest in this paper namely Canada, Kenya and the United States all signed the Paris Agreement in 2015. Canada ratified the Paris Agreements with no overwhelming surprise since they had also taken part in the 1992 Declaration on Environment and Development, the 2005 Kyoto Protocols and the 2020 Copenhagen Accords (Perspective on Climate Change Action in Canada). However, the country has failed to meet the emission reduction targets it had for each one of those climate change global gatherings. Although Canada is taking part in all these events, the question has been asked several times on whether the political administration was doing the most to reach these goals. Data also shows the wide variety of greenhouse gas production from one province to the next which could potentially explain why Canada has such a difficult time meeting these objectives. While Canada's image benefits from ratifying all these treaties, the fact that it seems unable to meet its objective repeatedly may hurt the country's credibility in the long run.

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Kenya is also one of the 194 countries that have endorsed the Paris Agreements. A priori Kenya had a lot of reasons to join in on the treaty: not only was it allowing the country to develop new causes of energy instead of overusing non-reusable sources, but it would be able to put policies into work since there would be funding for emerging states from which Kenya is a part of (Cobenefits 2021, 10). While many nations have a hard time committing to climate change regulations since the consequences seem to be abstract, uncertain, and happening in the long term, Kenya has very concrete examples of the effect climate crisis will have on its people. The people living in the Nzoia River, for example, have already suffered some outcomes in the form of droughts, floods, and the activation of volcanoes in the region (Onencan 2018). Water management issues are also an important concern for Kenyans which led up to different types of initiatives and ideas such as the Climate-Smart Agriculture framework which is meant to reconsider the way agriculture is practised to better adapt to climate change. The main difficulty for Kenya's implementation of the policies that were thought through after they signed the Paris Agreements comes from its dependency on industrialized countries committed to their promise to sustain emerging countries in their climate change response, which has not yet been done to the measure they had agreed to in 2015 (Onencan 2018).

Although the US signed the Paris Agreements under Barack Obama's presidency, his successor, Donald Trump did not consider his nation to benefit from having adopted the legally binding document; in 2020, the country formally withdrew its ratification of the treaty (McGrath 2020). Obama's administration had pledged to reduce global greenhouse emissions by 26-28% by 2025 and to financially support arising states in establishing their environmental regulations by transferring 3 billion dollars their way (Pros and Cons of the Paris Climate Change Agreements for America). Trump believed that such promises would put the country at a disadvantage since limiting the global greenhouse effects would hurt high polluting American industries which were essential not only in their nature but since they employed a lot of citizens (Pros and Cons of the Paris Climate Change Agreements for America). While the former decision of being part of the agreements was received positively by both the international community and Americans, the latter faced plenty of opposition. The US, at the time of their ratification of the treaty, was alone responsible for 15% of all greenhouse emissions on the planet; for them to join on the aims of the Paris Agreements was meaningful and encouraging in terms of the global goal of fighting climate change (McGrath 2020). With their retraction, the US not only opened a door for other endorsers to abandon their commitments but predisposed the trust additional approvers had in the state. Americans were mostly hurt by this decision, and many private companies promised the public that they would keep on limiting their greenhouse emissions with the same spirit they had under Obama's administration; the opinion to withdraw from the Paris Agreements, was, therefore, one that affected the presidency's leadership (McGrath 2020).

Through the framework of environmental justice, it is revealing to contrast and compare the three states' relationships to the Paris Agreements of 2015. While the three countries were part of the agreements, their approach was different: Canada signed, irrespectively, and their actual motivation to implement the treaty's commitment is questionable; Kenya also signed with an urge to act on climate change costs that are already being lived in the sub-Saharan state but depended on industrialized countries financial support to make the policies happen; the US signed conversely a change in administration made the state adopt a much more protectionist perspective, therefore retracting from the protocol it had previously signed. Canada and the US seem less encouraged by climate change concerns arguably because they have not had as harsh environmental consequences in their nations yet and feel like it is a matter that could be dealt with more seriously later. Since these countries are also economic power, they have all the resources disposable to them when they decide to implement eco-friendly policies. Kenya is very far from those realities. Not only does it already suffer from climate change, but it lacks the fund to develop policies that would increase its adaptability and capacity to respond to the natural disasters they are addressing. Climate change affects each country differently and

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those countries do not have equal resources to face it. Kenya is suffering a disproportionate number of natural disasters because of climate change and cannot remediate the situation without industrialized nations' involvement; while the US merely cancelled any support they would have offered to those states, they are quite simply abandoning countries like Kenya to their faith (Climate Action Tracker). Not only is this treatment unfair but it raises questions about environmental racism.

CASE STUDY

LEAD POISONING IN OWINA UHURU AND FLINT

Collective community action, transparency, and accountability to address environmental injustices

In different parts of the world, communities predisposed by environmental pollution are taking collective action to seek justice. Owina Uhuru in Kenya and Flint city in Michigan, United States are examples of communities that have challenged government institutions, private corporations, and individuals for contributing to lead poisoning in these communities, which has led to the death of many people and left residents with critical health conditions. With lead-poisoning accounting for 0.90 million deaths globally in 2019, it can be regarded as a public health and environmental problem with its impact seen especially in marginalized and black communities.

In 2020, the Land and Environment Court in Mombasa awarded 1.3 billion Kshs (which is the equivalent of 12 million USD) as compensation to residents of Owina Uhuru affected by lead poisoning. The compensation is a product of a 2016 class-action suit filed on behalf of 3,000 residents for harm suffered because of the pollution from Metal Refinery (EPZ), a smelting factory recycling used lead-acid batteries in the community.

The judgment declared that “the pollution incident constituted violations of the right to life, health, water, and a clean and healthy environment” of the people of Owina Uhuru (Mwanza, 2021). The celebrated “landmark judgment” climaxed a series of complaints, campaigns and legal battles by environmental activists, factory workers and community members. Preceding the judgment, there were complaints about respiratory illnesses and the death of livestock by the people of the community. Government officials, in response, initially shut down the factory in June 2018 for polluting the community but allowed it to reopen. Intensified complaints in 2009 pushed Kenyan environmental officials to investigate, and they reported that the factory was built without an environmental impact assessment. By 2014 when EPZ was finally shut down, its activities had led to the deaths of over 300 children and 50 adults because of lead poisoning (Ruth, 2022). The efforts of the community through made the government more accountable and transparent about environmental pollution. However, residents are still waiting for justice as the compensation is yet to be paid.

In a similar case of lead poisoning that has been widely reported in the media, the city of Flint, Michigan where over 60% of the population is Black exemplifies how local community action is key to bringing issues of environmental injustices and violation of human rights to the fore. As part of a cost-saving strategy in 2014, the city of Michigan switched the city water supplier from the Detroit Water and Sewerage Department to source water from the Flint River.

A few months later, residents reported a change in the colour and smell of the water. A series of tests conducted revealed that household water contains a dangerously high level of lead, which was caused by the corrosion of the water pipes. Even with scientific evidence and several complaints of water contamination by the people, the city initially refused to switch back to the Detroit Water System. Instead, the city of Flint issued boil-water advisories after bacteria and carcinogenic substances were detected in the water. With multiple research that considered the water unsafe and unhealthy for consumption and protests by residents, the city of Michigan switched back to the Detroit Water in October 2015.

IN DECEMBER 2015, RESIDENTS FILED A CLASS ACTION LAWSUIT AGAINST CITY OFFICIALS AND THE GOVERNOR OF MICHIGAN, CLAIMING THE CITY INTENTIONALLY EXPOSED THE PEOPLE TO CONTAMINATED WATER.

THESE CASE STUDIES IN KENYA AND THE UNITED STATES EXEMPLIFY THE FAILURE OF GOVERNMENT INSTITUTIONS IN PRIORITIZING THE HEALTH AND WELFARE OF BLACK PEOPLE AGAINST RISKS ASSOCIATED WITH ENVIRONMENTAL HAZARDS AND POLLUTION.

In December 2015, residents filed a class action lawsuit against city officials and the Governor of Michigan, claiming the city intentionally exposed the people to contaminated water. Subsequently, the city and President Obama declared a state of emergency and palliatives in the form of bottled drinking water were provided. Between 2016 and 2017, over six lawsuits and criminal charges were filed against government employees, the government of the city, private companies, environmental agencies, and schools for exposing the people of Flint to contaminated water. The efforts to hold the government and other stakeholders accountable resulted in the award of a \$626m settlement by a federal judge to victims of the lead water crisis in 2021 (Guardian Staff and Agencies, 2021). While there have been

claims that the Flint water is safe for drinking, the level of mistrust in the government has deepened further and many school children are left with neurological and behavioural challenges caused by exposure to lead from drinking water (Green, 2019). The Flint water problem demonstrates deep environmental injustice as the 2016 Flint Water Advisory Task Force Report 2016 states that “Flint’s poor, largely African American population did not enjoy the same degree of protection from environmental hazards as that provided to other communities” (Davis, Kolb, Reynolds, Rothstein, & Sikkema, 2016).

These case studies in Kenya and the United States exemplify the failure of government institutions in prioritizing the health and welfare of Black people against risks associated with environmental hazards and pollution. It also demonstrates that collective action is perhaps a starting point in seeking justice for communities impacted by environmental challenges. However, for environmental injustices to be sustainably addressed, Black communities need support from multilateral institutions to tackle institutionalized environmental injustices. The Permanent Forum for People of African Descent (PFPAD), an organ of the United Nations tasked with “improving the safety and quality of life and livelihoods of people of African descent” can document cases of environmental injustices in Black communities around the world, collaborate with national governments and marginalized communities to provide expert advice on strategies to address unfair treatment of people in these communities. As environmental injustices are violations of human rights of people, the PFPAD is well positioned to provide policy framework and instruments that can help protect Black communities from being violated and legal support to community-seeking redress for being exposed to hazards and environmental-related impacts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It's important to take cognizance of the global debate on the extent of environmental and health impacts of lead poisoning regarding environmental justice. Many countries including the USA, Canada, and Germany must revise their lead goals and intervention levels following emerging information and from the case studies discussions, we can infer that there are consistently more lead concentrations in the environment i.e., the soil, and water citing examples from the lead-acid battery recycling factory in Uhuru Owino slums in Kenya and the Flint River in the USA. This can be attributed to the factory processes which result in lead leakages into nearby places engaging the very populous low-income housing.

There is a need to unfailingly research and generate new knowledge to convey innovative standards and policies. This is to mean that, there is a necessity for the continual effect of lead reduction in industrial working practices and litigation. Programs aimed at addressing this issue should target homes especially those vulnerable to irresponsible lead waste disposal and additional sources of pollution. Investigations and periodic audits in such industrial areas, as provided by the law, require to be enforced and upscaled. Other individual-level behavioural measures need to be embraced to diminish the hazard of lead poisoning. This calls for substantive investment in the education of at-risk communities. These regional recommendations are foundational for the United Nations, Donor/Member States, philanthropy, host country governments, INGOs, and local NGOs to implement.

Environmental Justice and Racism

Regarding environmental justice, we propose policies to address the impacts of environmental racism and close the health equity gap including promoting ongoing engagement among multiple sectors to institutionalize health equity goals. As the lead poisoning case study for Kenya and the United States has demonstrated, systemic racism has proven that it affects the government from helping minorities, when representation is inadequate. The Decade of People of African Descent has clarified the importance of interpretation, international, nation, and regional government in implementing non-bias, racism and discriminatory regulation that favour certain groups while depriving them of the same benefits.

Additionally, we suggest ongoing data collection that measures racial inequities in healthcare services and accessibility to supply the foundation for political action and accountability on the determinants. The United States has illustrated a pattern of lack of interventions when mainly injured parties are African American or other visible minorities. For example, after the catastrophe of Hurricane Katrina devastation, the American government was criticized for not providing sufficient help to those in need. Furthermore, the government has not fixed the lead poisoning in Flint, Michigan. These are instances of the government not assisting certain communities because of the apparent absence of interest or benefits.

Green Economy

We suggest that a policy framework that balances the competing demands of the economy and environment should be put in place, and countries should have economic approaches with a central focus on access to green finance, technology, and investments in terms of development and mainstreaming of macroeconomic to support the transition to a green economy. Kenya is currently one of the most involved partners in the Paris Agreement. However, the country is extremely suffering from the consequences of other nations not wanting to accept regulations that promote a green economy. An example of a country which lacks involvement during the Kyoto Protocol, or the United States back out from the Paris Agreement during the Trump Administration demonstrates one of the most developed country inconsistencies. Consequently, encouraging the government from adopting policies that conjoin the environment and economy would benefit both the country and the notion of sustainable development. Furthermore, it will encourage other nations to follow and develop their system of sustainable development.

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Migration and Food Security

We suggest that the government influence a relief action plan or committee to aid in food security and reduce migrations. In Kenya, many people have left their communities and families because of the lack of government assistance when it comes to food security. On the Other, the United States has a similar problem, does not suffer from high migration, rather poorer communities are ignored by their government; hence, creating a never-ended loop of food insecurity.

Moreover, we should work toward social addition and cohesion and foster inclusive and participatory processes on access to and use of natural resources. With the government providing more aid to the communities, it might strengthen their bond and therefore, decrease migration.

Low-Income Housing Proximity to Landfill and Highly Polluted Areas

We encourage the development agencies and funding that should consider the environmental impacts of their housing programmes and provision. Such assistance will contribute to the improvement of the overall quality of life of the recipients of the low-income housing programme, and in turn, to the overall sustainable development of the countries. The low-income housing projects should profit from the same benefits as any other community. The Owina Uhuru city in Kenya and Flint, Michigan are examples of the government not prioritizing where they decide to develop affordable housing. Therefore, we believe that the government should be held accountable for the consequences of its lack of research and action. Furthermore, there are very few regulations, judicial instruments, or technical guidelines addressing matters relating to low-income housing, accordingly, promoting accountability can incentivize the government to adopt the best policies that should be increased and implemented.

Environmental Colonialism

Regarding environmental colonialism, large conservation NGOs and international donors that fund conservation initiatives in former colonies must be held to account for the harms fortress conservation policies have disproportionately inflicted on some of the world's most marginalized and environmentally conscious communities. They must do so by providing effective mechanisms for victims of fortress conservation to seek redress, providing adequate restitution and compensation. For instance, the people from Flint and Uhuru Owino in Kenya and the United States respectively.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, environmental justice and colonialism are key elements to the wellness and advancement of people of African descent. The decade of people of African descent is as proclaimed by the general assembly a decade for people of African descent to receive recognition, justice and development. This aims to shed light on the many contributions that people of African descent have brought to society and all the many accomplishments. The decade of people of African descent also aims at correcting and fighting all injustices that the people of African descent may and will continue facing.

The lead poisoning case study has demonstrated that environmental justice is directly associated with environmental racism. The history of colonialism and slavery of both nations has demonstrated that low-income housing development receives poorer resources from their government because of their lack of profits. In consequence, those communities suffer from an increase in food insecurity and migration. To recognize the multiple issues is the first step toward creating and finding effective ways to bring justice to those who need it and give justice to those who have wronged it. Subsequently, because of Kenya's historical past, the impact of environmental injustice promoted migration and food insecurity within the country.

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Along with the low supply of housing and the uprise in inflation in the housing market. It is now harder than ever to buy a home. “Affordable housing” comes with a cost. The health of those living in those areas, a high percentage being African Americans who occupy low-paying and low-security jobs. This produces a never-ending cycle of poverty and disease that affects generation after generation unless a change is made.

In this specific crisis of Flint, Michigan, lead poisoning, the water has been contaminated with lead and maybe legionella bacteria making it impossible for the residents to drink water and use it to shower and other water uses. As this was something done by the city to cut costs and unfortunately has cost the people of flint their livelihood. On a national level, flint has been addressed many times in the white house and they have vowed to make reparations for this failure of the state to take care of its own. On the other hand, in the Owina Uhuru case in Kenya, which is mainly a homogenous racial country, the government is more likely not to intervene sooner because of segregated housing based on income.

Consequently, by recommending that countries adopt our recommendations, we are trying to remove any opportunities for international, national, and regional governments from adopting systemic racism behaviours.

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